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Faculty of Medicine, University of Banja Luka, the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia & Herzegovina

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Metabolic Syndrome Treatment - Bile Acids Role

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Abstract

Metabolic syndrome is a collection of five phenotypes: hypertension, hyperglycemia, hypertriglyceridemia, insulin resistance and obesity. Many of these metabolic phenotypes are associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Bile acids are a group of structurally diverse molecules, the chief components of bile, that are synthesized in the liver from cholesterol and further metabolized in gut contents (more than 560 so far). The principal bile acids in humans are: 1. primary bile acids: cholic acid (CA), chenodeoxycholic acid (CDCA) and their glycine and taurine conjugates 2. secondary bile acids (produced by gut bacteria): deoxycholic acid (DA), lithocholic acid (LA). Our discovery and patent in year 2000 changed the attitude towards the role bile acids into potential treatments for Diabetes mellitus. Experimental studies in our laboratories have shown that bile acid derivatives like 3a,7a-dihydroxy-12-keto-5b-cholanate (MKC) is useful as hypolipemic and hypoglycemic agents given alone or in the combination with probiotic bacteria. Its combination with gliclazide worked as antihyperglycemic agent in the experimental Diabetes mellitus type 1. The action of MKC arises due to an effect on transport at the membrane level as well as metabolic processes regulation. The advantage of MKC over the other bile acids is that it has low toxicity and may be used as an adjuvant to improve the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties of other drugs. The emerging evidence in the past decade has pointed to the role of bile acids as signalling, endocrine molecules that regulate the glucose, lipid, and energy metabolism through complex and interrelated pathways that mainly include FXR and TGR5. Targeting the interactions between bile acids, microbiota, and bile acid receptors signalling seems to derive an approach for the treatment of metabolic diseases. The investigation of novel bile acid-based ligands in the light of metabolic syndrome treatment, much attention has been paid to the development of bile acid derivatives with reduced toxicity. Bile acids and their derivatives are promising new drug candidates for the metabolic syndrome treatment.

Key words: Bile acids; Diabetes; Metabolic syndrome.

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